

FAILURE ANALYSIS OF SANDWICH COMPOSITES WITH CHOPPED FIBER REINFORCEMENT UNDER IN-PLANE COMPRESSION

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ABSTRACT

The interfacial delamination of the face/core interface of the sandwich composites is one of the often-encountered failure modes for the structures being in manufacturing or under service loads. Sandwich specimens are manufactured using the low pressure contact moulding process. The chopped fibers are inserted into the interface between the face sheet and the core with the resin flow. The experimental test and finite element model are employed to study the failure process of sandwich specimens under compression load. The interface element is adopted to simulate the the interface crack growth. The Hashin failure criterion and degradation principle are used for failure analysis of the composite face sheet. So, different failure modes, such as the buckling, crack proration and face sheet local failure, are taken into account in the analysis. The agreements between the present numerical and experimental results show the validity of present analysis model and method. The results show that the interfacial toughening measure can enhance the bearing capacity and improve damage tolerant of the sandwich composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced sandwich composite materials / structures with high specific strength, high specific stiffness and special function, has been widely used in military field and civilian engineering. However, the core and face sheets are generally bonded by weak performance resin. The bonding layer fracture occurs frequently in the service process. The interfacial crack would affect the integrity of sandwich structures and reduce stiffness and bearing capacity. Furthermore, the interfacial crack can induce other failure modes and lead to the premature failure [1].

Currently, there are mainly two types of method to improve the interfacial performance of sandwich composites, namely the chemical and physical methods. The chemical method improve the interface by changing the morphology or components of the interface material for instance using high performance adhesive material, the chemical treatment of the core material, etc. The physical method employ sewing or reinforced materials mixed in the interface to form enhanced macro or micro structure.

One of the macro improving methods for the sandwich structure is introduced by means of additional structure form to prevent the propagation of face/core delamination. Jakobsen et al [2] presented a peel stopper concept for the interfacial reinforcement of sandwich structures. Some like flanged beams of sub-structural component were embedded into the sandwich structures. The toughening mechanism is to arrest face/core interfacial crack propagation by rerouting the crack path into a restricted area of the sandwich structure, thus to prevent the spreading of the delamination into the remaining parts of the sandwich structure. Nevertheless, the sub-structural component increases not only the weight of the structures, but also the manufacturing cost.

Z-pin method is a typical toughening process that employs the needle-like material through the thickness of the sandwich composites to reinforce the interface. 1980s, Tomashevskii et al [3] proposed

Z-pin method using fiber bundle and make it to be automated. At the same time, Aztex company invented the Ultrasonically Assisted Z-pin (UAZ) fiber technology, which was the most widely used in commerce and industry. Dai et al [4] performed the Z-pin pull-out test to measure the loading-displacement curve. The experiment verified the Z-pin bridging effects and confirmed its toughening mechanism. In recent years, Z-pin method has been applied to composite sandwich structures. Nanayakkara et al [5] measured the out-plane performance of foam core sandwich structures with Z-pin toughening under compression loading. They found that Z-pin can significantly improve the compression stiffness and crushing load of the structures. Mostafa et al[6] employed different angles of the Z-pin to enhance the shear performance of the foam core sandwich structures. The finite element analysis of elastic shear stiffness and ultimate load showed that ± 600 Z-pin can provide optimal shear performance.

The chopped fiber toughening method, which was initially proposed by Sohn, Walker and Hu [7, 8], combine the advantages of both Z-pin and hybrid method. The Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) and End-Notched Flexure (ENF) experiment have been performed to measure the critical energy release rate of carbon fiber/epoxy laminates with chopped Kevlar fiber reinforcement. The results showed that the interface crack energy release rate of mode I and mode II were both raised more than double. Some scholars (Wang et al [9], Cantwell et al [10]) have extended the method to toughening the face/core interface of the composite sandwiches. The mode I critical energy release rate of the face/core interface has increased by 20%-75%.

This study presents the experimental and numerical results of composite sandwich specimens consisting of two face layers and the aluminium foam core with pre-crack at the interface. The compression behaviour for specimens with or without reinforcement is determined. The analysis models that take face sheet strength failure, face sheet buckling and interface crack growth into account are conducted to characterize the failure process. The comparison between experimental and numerical results shows the validation of the model presented in the study. These outcomes provide an insight which can contribute to a better understanding of the interfacial toughness reinforcement of sandwich structures.

2 EXPERIMENT PROCEDURE

The experimental configuration of specimens with or without reinforcement for in-plane compression test is shown in Fig.1. Sandwich composite specimens are manufactured by low-pressure contact molding process. The laminated face sheet are made of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy in a $[(0,90)/(\pm 45)]_s$ configuration and with 0.5mm thickness. The core material is Aluminum foams with a weight of 500kg/m^3 .

For reinforced specimens, a chopped Kevlar fiber film is inserted between the face sheets and the core. Then a strip of Teflon is used to create the artificial initial crack between the core and the face sheet. The panels are cured for 24 hours at room temperature. The cured panels are subsequently machined to specimens with the width of 20 mm and the length of 100 mm, and the loading fixture are super-glued by using the cyanoacrylate.

Fig.1. Schematic of composite sandwich specimen with interfacial crack

The compression testing is performed by means of a SANS testing machine with a 200 N load-sensor under the displacement control mode. The displacement loading rate is set as 1 mm/min to control the crack propagation, and each specimen stop loading when the crack propagated to the end of the specimens or the face sheet is complete failure.

3 THEORY AND MODEL

3.1 Finite element model

According to the experimental observation, the sandwich specimen under in-plane compression will be failure for local strength, lost stability, or for both. The change of the interface toughness will alternate the failure mechanism.

Fig.2. Finite element model of the sandwich specimen

For the analysis of the difference failure modes of sandwich specimen under in-plane compression, a detailed finite element discretization for the three dimensions is employed. An initial crack is inserted into the interface between the face and core. For the sake of simplicity, the face sheet and core are discretized by shell element and solid element, respectively, as shown in Fig.2. The interface elements are placed along the interface between the face sheet and the core to capture the interfacial crack growth in the sandwich specimens.

3.2 Failure criterion

The strength failure of the face sheet in the delamination area will easily occur when the sandwich composite specimens under the in-plane compressive loading. The stiffness degradation models based on the Hashin criterion are employed. The criterion which is described by the stress components can estimate the in-plane damage accurately compared with the experimental results. The Mindlin first order shear theory is used to calculate the stress of each layer. If the Hashin criterion is satisfied, the stiffness will reduce. When the element stress exceeds the material strength, the element will be deleted from the finite element model. Specific failure criteria are as follows:

Tensile failure of fiber ($\sigma_{11} \geq 0$)

$$e_f^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_T}\right)^2 + \alpha \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_L}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (1)$$

Compression failure of fiber ($\sigma_{11} < 0$)

$$e_f^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_C}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (2)$$

Tensile failure of matrix ($\sigma_{22} \geq 0$)

$$e_m^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S_L}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (3)$$

Compression failure of matrix ($\sigma_{22} < 0$)

$$e_m^2 = \left(\frac{\sigma_{22}}{2S_T}\right)^2 \left[\left(\frac{Y_C}{2S_T}\right)^2 - 1 \right] \frac{\sigma_{22}}{Y_C} + \frac{\tau_{12}}{S_L} \geq 1 \quad (4)$$

where e_f, e_m is the failure factor of fiber and matrix, respectively. X_T, X_C is the longitudinal tension and compression strength. Y_T, Y_C is the transverse tension and compression strength. S_L, S_T is the longitudinal and transverse shear strength. α is the contribution factor of the shear stress on the tensile failure. When the material damage occurs in the element, the damage operator is introduced into the constitutive equations

$$C_d = \frac{1}{D} \begin{bmatrix} (1-d_f)E_1 & (1-d_f)(1-d_m)\mu_{21}E_1 & 0 \\ (1-d_f)(1-d_m)\mu_{12}E_2 & (1-d_m)E_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & D(1-d_s)G_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where d_f, d_m, d_s are the damage status variables of fiber, matrix and shear, respectively. The value of status variables are decided by the energy dissipation of the material breaking.

3.3 Interface element based on the cohesive zone model

An arbitrary crack system can be divided into two parts: one corresponds to the physical length of the stress-free crack; the other one is the cohesive zone, where damage of the material occurs and finite cohesive tractions follow a certain law: including linear, bilinear, parabolic and exponential laws, etc. The cohesive zone model is usually implemented in the finite element approach by the interface element. The interface element, which has zero initial thickness in the un-deformed configuration, can model the interface delamination between continuum elements. Elements in the model are 4-noded, with two displacement degrees of freedom per node for 2D. The relative displacements of the nodes are used to characterize the deformation, and damage occurs only in the cohesive elements which obey the linear constitutive relation.

The nodal force vector and tangent stiffness matrix are defined as

$$\mathbf{f}_N^{el} = W \int_{-1}^1 \mathbf{B}^T \boldsymbol{\Theta} \mathbf{t}_{loc} \det \mathbf{J} d\xi \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{K}^{el} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{f}_N^{el}}{\partial \mathbf{d}^{el}} = -W \int_{-1}^1 \mathbf{B}^T \Theta \mathbf{D}_{loc} \Theta^T \mathbf{B} \det \mathbf{J} d\zeta \quad (7)$$

where: W is the width of the interface element; Θ represents the matrix of direction cosines transforming the local coordinate system to the global one; \mathbf{t}_{loc} is the cohesive traction vector; $\det \mathbf{J}$ is the Jacobian determinant; \mathbf{D}_{loc} is the stiffness matrix

3.4 Implicit dynamic equation and displacement compatibility condition

The discretization of the elastic body into finite element and the assembly of all element contributions into global matrices and vectors lead to the following matrix-vector equation

$$\mathbf{M} \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{U}} + \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{U} = \mathbf{F} \quad (8)$$

where \mathbf{M} is the mass matrix, \mathbf{K} is the stiffness matrix and \mathbf{F} is the right-hand side vector of the prescribed forces. The vector $\mathbf{U}=\mathbf{U}(t)$ is the global vector of nodal displacements. For the numerical solution of this second-order differential equation, we discretize the time interval in finite steps of size and calculate the approximate solution on times $t_{n+1}=t_n+\Delta t$.

Based on Mindlin postulation, the displacements at any point within the shell element is

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, z) &= u_0(x) + z\theta_y(x) \\ v(x, z) &= v_0(x) - z\theta_x(x) \\ w(x, z) &= w_0(x) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where u_0, v_0, w_0 are the displacements at mid-plane of face in local coordinate system. θ_x and θ_y are the angle of rotation of mid-plane normal deformation in local coordinate system. Cohesive layer element and the shell element are connected through the nodes displacement continuous conditions.

The nonlinear contact element is employed to avoid the unreasonable overlap of the face sheet and the core under compression load.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.3. Experimental and numerical results for sandwich specimens with and without toughening

The compression displacement is applied to the specimens, while the corresponding reaction force at the loading point can be obtained by calculation. The experimental and numerical results of the compression load versus displacement at the load points are shown in Fig.3. The dash curve represents the experimental and numerical results without reinforcement and the solid curves represent the results with reinforcement, respectively. It can be seen: (1) the curves depict three regions i.e. elastic region, local failure region after reaching peak load and subsequent failure region; (2) Comparing with the specimens without reinforcement, the maximum critical load has been improved in the elastic region. The chopped fiber can prevent the initial failure of sandwich specimens under the in-plane compression load. (3) The face sheet buckling lead to the load decline for both specimens. For the specimens without reinforcement, the load continues to decrease with the crack growth. However, due to the closure tractions exerted by the chopped fiber, the specimens still keep high carrying capacity

before face sheet strength failure. This indicates that specimens with the interfacial reinforcement are much more damage tolerant than specimens without reinforcement.

Fig.4. the failure modes of sandwich specimens with and without toughening under in-plane compression load

The failure modes of composite sandwich specimens under in-plane compression load are shown in Fig.4. Fig.4.(1)A-C represent the experimental and numerical results without reinforcement, respectively. Fig.4.(2)A-C represent the experimental and numerical results with reinforcement, respectively. It can be seen (1) the face sheet and core occurs elastic deformation in the initial compression load. The performance mismatch between the face sheet and core lead to the uncoordinated deformation. The core and face sheets occur plastic compressible deformation and buckling, respectively. The maximum stresses are found around the face sheet middle, but the failure has not yet occurred. The interfacial crack growth is not occurred for the both specimens.

(2) the local failure occurs with the displacement increasing. Fig.4.(1)B and (2)B corresponding to the A-B stage shows that the interfacial crack continue growing for the specimens without reinforcement. The face sheet middle is in high stress state, but remains undamaged. Fig.4.(2) B shows that the face sheet occurs failure after the interface crack grow in small length. This indicates that the chopped fiber can improve the interfacial strength and toughness to prevent the crack growth of the face/core interface.

(3) Fig.4.(1)C and (2)C shows that the subsequent failure stages. The interface crack nearly grows to the whole specimen length for the specimens without reinforcement. The longer free length of face sheet leads to the lower load-bearing capacity of the sandwich specimens. For the specimens with reinforcement, the local face sheets are complete failure. The reinforced specimens can remain high load-bearing capacity in this stage, only the core continues plastic compressing.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The reinforced effects of chopped fiber toughening method on interfacial of composite sandwiches under in-plane compression are studied by experimental and numerical methods. The failure criterion and interface element are adopted to describe the process of face sheet failure and interfacial crack growth. It is verified that numerical results presented good agreement with the theory and experimental work. The results indicate that the chopped fiber could effectively reduce the debonding area at interface under loading, keep structural integrity and thus increase the peak load and energy absorption ability of sandwich composites. The interactive influence of different failure mechanisms become essential to choose the reinforced material and technology process for the interface toughening of the composite sandwich structures.

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